

SUGGESTING AN INSTITUTIONAL DATA REPOSITORY FOR THE UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN

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Kayleigh Roos¹, Erika Mias¹ Jason van Rooyen²

¹ Digital Library Services

² eResearch

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MISSION STATEMENT

The UCT Institutional Data Repository (IDR) will serve principal investigators at the University of Cape Town in need of a repository to preserve and openly disseminate data that support their published research findings. The repository service is provided in terms of the UCT Research Data Management Policy (in draft). It will preserve curated datasets and make them accessible through persistent identifiers linking to their respective scholarly publications accessible on OpenUCT or elsewhere. UCT's IDR is intended to become an accredited trusted digital repository (TDR).

The UCT IDR aims to accommodate a breadth of data types across all research disciplines. It will focus primarily on supporting all researchers without access to an existing discipline-specific repository. Very large datasets associated with published work will be supported if possible when they cannot be accommodated elsewhere.

The UCT IDR will provide open access to research data files, making them available for download in standard formats. In order to ensure the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of the data, high quality documentation and metadata will be required at the time of collection. Abiding by the institutional guidelines, quality standards and curation practises of local discipline communities at UCT will also be a requirement for publication in the UCT IDR.

CONSIDERATIONS

Potential repository solutions will be evaluated based on several criteria that we outline below. These are principally capabilities or functions of the software that are essential for meeting the UCT IDR's mission and addressing the potential needs of the research community. External factors that will influence the design and support of the solution, such as institutional support, infrastructure and financial sustainability, are also discussed.

Considerations for choosing a software solution for the UCT IDR are (in no particular order):

Storage

Both the ownership and the location of the storage backing the UCT IDR have important implications for the choice of solution. If it is expected that new storage will be purchased and dedicated to housing the repository data, then a locally hosted, open-source repository software solution is feasible. The only other alternative is a hosted, software-as-a-service (SaaS) solution, which offers cloud-based storage, as well as complete management of the repository for a fee. Commercial SaaS solutions tend to be very expensive, but have very low start-up costs and no capital expenditure. It is important to consider salaries of IT staff and replacement costs of infrastructure when comparing a locally hosted and managed repository solution to a commercial SaaS solution. Recovery of storage costs from researchers is also something that needs to be considered in light of the desire to make eResearch services sustainable.

Infrastructure, Operation and Maintenance

The different repository solutions investigated in this report offer a variety of features, but also have associated levels of complexity concerning their installation, customisation, and operation. These range from the simplest SaaS models, where all maintenance and sometimes even training is handled by a third-party, to the most complex local installations, requiring multiple servers and extensive in-house programming experience. Local staff capacity is therefore an essential consideration if the UCT IDR is to be a sustainable, quality service to the local research community. In addition to the IT staff required to handle installation and

server maintenance, provisions are needed for trainers and data managers, who are critical to the uptake of data management services.

Equally important is the size of the national and international community using and supporting the various repository software solutions, as well as the financial model supporting the development of the software. There is a lot to learn from larger communities, both in terms of troubleshooting installation and configuration, but also in terms of best practise for research data management and publishing of research data. At the local level, choosing a repository software solution that is going to be suitable for other higher education institutions to deploy will allow a greater degree of exchange and collaboration between repository owners and national funding initiatives.

Publication Workflow

Unlike the traditional paper-based publications, where peer-review is employed to vet data quality, research data can only be validated by experts equipped with knowledge of the discipline-specific standards, who potentially have to reprocess/analyse the data to assess its quality. Feedback from the community of users who download data from the UCT IDR is therefore the only mechanism to directly measure data quality. Forums - where available in repository software - allow this type of feedback, but will have to be consistently moderated to ensure that authors have a fair chance of replying to any criticism of their data.

Metadata, which is crucial to the findability and reusability of the data, can be evaluated at the time of submission, but again, requires experts equipped with standards that have been agreed upon by the respective research communities. Since it seems unlikely that domain-specific data managers can be hired for each envisaged community of researchers that will publish data in the UCT IDR, curation communities will be essential for this purpose. The same communities can also assist with user support, as well as training in data deposition. Several of the repository software solutions presented here offer curation workflows, where designated members of communities can manage the submission process and have authority to only approve datasets with correct documentation. The implementation of custom metadata is critical for communities wanting to enforce high quality standards in their data collections. Privacy and embargo features also need to be included in the publication workflow in a

university environment, because of the number of privately-funded projects and the temporary presence of students (see Sharing below).

Dissemination

One of the principal drivers for implementing the UCT IDR is to ensure that UCT researchers funded by the NRF have a place to store their research data in accordance with the proposed ¹[open access mandate](#). It therefore seems likely that all data in the repository will be open access, after a period of privileged use if requested, and need to be persistently available and citeable through unique persistent identifiers. The ability to issue or fetch ²[DOIs](#) for datasets, as well as interoperability with the envisaged ³NRF harvesting system, is the only way to ensure that these outputs are linked to researcher records in the NRF database. Ensuring that DOIs point to specific datasets, rather than merely the most recent versions of reprocessed data, is essential and will require versioning capabilities. The decision of what to issue DOIs for is complex - to issue a DOI for each distinct item in a dataset may, in many instances, be unnecessarily resource-intensive, but on the other hand, only issuing DOIs at collection level makes reuse difficult and potentially discourages citation. One solution is the ability to group items from and/or across datasets into baskets and issue DOIs for these user-based ‘ad-hoc’ collections.

Further consideration needs to be given on the manner in which datasets will be linked to their originating studies in other journals or open-access repositories, as UCT may not house all manuscripts published by UCT authors. Generally, since researchers prefer to publish in

¹ <http://www.nrf.ac.za/media-room/news/statement-open-access-research-publications-national-research-foundation-nrf-funded>

² <https://www.datacite.org/dois.html>

³ The NRF is the national provider of DOIs for research data. They have negotiated an agreement with DataCite to issue DOIs to South African HEIs, and other affiliated institutions, free of charge. For the HEI to issue NRF minted DataCite DOIs there are two options:

- 1) A scheduled **harvesting** system initiated by the NRF, where the NRF can harvest OAI-PMH metadata via the repository API. DOIs are then assigned, verified and registered with DataCite, and the updated records are sent back via the API. DOIs are only made available/visible in the repository once this process is complete. The repository is only aware of potential issues with DOI validation at the end of this process.
- 2) The repository is able to assign DOIs provisionally to the data (immediately visible) and the repository manager performs a **push-through** service where the OAI-PMH metadata is submitted to the NRF system. The NRF then validates and registers the DOI with DataCite. The DOIs are immediately validated, or error reports are sent to the repository flagging problems with data/datasets.

The use of this service requires that all NRF data are labelled as such in the OAI-PMH metadata (under e.g.: “funder” field) so that the NRF can identify NRF research outputs hosted elsewhere and register the link to the dataset in their repository.
<https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>

peer/community-recognised journals, the effort to collect links to research publications will reside with the depositor or repository managers, and journal copyright considerations will further limit what can be published locally. This is clearly one of several areas of concern where strategic, scholarly and legal matters deeply intersect with those of information-technical infrastructure. Nonetheless, the ability of the UCT IDR to link directly from the dataset to the original research article is desirable, for which linking through unambiguous metadata references (authorship, title, page numbers etc. and possibly even a plain-text copy of the abstract) constitutes the minimum acceptable solution. In addition to DOIs, integration with disambiguation services like ⁴[ORCID](http://orcid.org/) is also important because of the emphasis on researcher profiles in UCT's new research administration system, Converis, as well as the interest shown in ORCID IDs by the NRF.

Although accreditation as a trusted digital repository is not an immediate goal, the choice of repository software should not preclude this. Appearing in aggregated list services, such as ⁵[Re3Data](http://www.re3data.org/), is important for findability of data and is therefore another reason to strive for certification. Actual duplication of data for long-term security/preservation will require regional/national community agreement on choice of repository software, if ⁶[LOCKSS](https://www.lockss.org/) will be the solution.

Reporting

A popular argument used to promote (rather than enforce) data publication is the fact that data in itself is useful (if made reusable), and that citations linking to the resource, or even downloads of the files, should be considered when evaluating the impact of a body of research work. Such statistics complement traditional (and increasingly outmoded) journal impact factors used to estimate an article's (and by inference a study's) importance. From an institutional point of view, it is advisable to calculate such statistics, both to inform the management of research activities at the university, as well as enable researchers to evaluate their own impacts and enhance their researcher profiles. The ability to link with systems like ⁷[Altmetric](https://www.altmetric.com/) and disambiguators like ORCID, is in this case a necessary feature. Raising the

⁴ <http://orcid.org/>

⁵ <http://www.re3data.org/>

⁶ <https://www.lockss.org/>

⁷ <https://www.altmetric.com/>

profile of research and researchers, at least at a local level, can also be achieved through repository showcases of featured datasets (such as ‘most downloaded’). Being able to create communities within the UCT IDR (with unique branding) can also contribute to a sense of community within a very diverse group of repository users.

Preservation and Archiving

The future obligations to the authors and the users of the datasets residing in the UCT IDR are very important to consider. The period of time for which the UCT IDR commits to keeping data available, and in what formats, are complicating factors. For instance, providing merely passive access to raw data files may not allow the actual data themselves to be reused, unless the associated software and libraries are also preserved. The ability to store software and even to track versions during software development is an important feature in support of this goal; as is the preference for open formats - seeing as the UCT IDR is envisaged to principally be an open access repository. Versioning of datasets and changes to metadata records, as well as the ability to download earlier versions of datasets, is also critical to helping establish and maintain the veracity of data stored within a repository. Once decided, the extent of the institutional commitment to preservation and archiving needs to be laid out in user agreements, and made available on the UCT IDR landing page (see Policy section below).

The NRF mandate does not specify a length of time to retain data in open access repositories, but precedents do exist around the world. Germany, for example, requires all research data to be kept for 10 years. The availability of functionalities for integrating the repository software with preservation and archiving tools is therefore critical in this regard. Where repository software does not make ample provision for long-term data preservation, integration with preservation systems, like ⁸[Archivematica](https://www.archivematica.org/en/), must be considered. Equivalently, implementation of LOCKSS redundancy cannot be achieved without tight integration into community-wide IDR solutions.

The sustainability and longevity of SaaS solutions are particularly important to assess, as they have direct implications for the future accessibility of data stored in a repository. Free, online repository solutions (‘hosted’ SaaS’s) have to include contingencies for the replacement of

⁸ <https://www.archivematica.org/en/>

hardware at the end of its lifecycle (3-5 years), or subscription fees in the case of platforms which do not own storage themselves, as well as rent from cloud vendors (e.g. ⁹[Amazon](https://www.amazon.co.uk/clouddrive/home/) or ¹⁰[RackSpace](https://www.rackspace.com/cloud/block-storage)). On the other hand, commercial SaaS's depend on the license fees they charge to fund the on-going costs of storing data, which is why they usually state upfront how long they will keep the data for. The popularity of the repository and the business model, however, ultimately determine the longevity of the service. Free hosted repository services are more complicated because they rely on external funding from philanthropic donors or funding agencies to sustain their services. Without ring-fenced funding for keeping data accessible after the main funding ends, data cannot be considered archived or preserved (in perpetuity). Contingency plans and funding models are therefore central considerations for implementing the UCT IDR.

Policy

Even if dedicated curation staff are employed, without the requisite research-disciplinary knowledge, data curators at the UCT IDR will not be able to vouch for the authenticity or accuracy of all submitted data. Responsibility will have to lie with the depositors, or their communities, and be legally secured in the form of a data statement and/or disclaimer that is/are deposited alongside each dataset. In addition to authenticity, privacy concerns surrounding human subject or otherwise ethically sensitive data will also require that depositors attest to the de-identification of the submitted data, since the UCT IDR staff cannot be held responsible for the contents of every dataset submitted.

It is equally important to ensure that downloaders of data from the UCT IDR acknowledge their responsibilities with regards to citing data upon reuse, and their acceptance of the ¹¹[open science copyright restrictions](http://opendefinition.org/guide/). Mechanisms such as pop-ups to track or enforce acceptance and acknowledgement of the proposed terms and conditions for publishing and accessing data in the UCT IDR are preferred over simply listing policies within or alongside the UCT IDR.

Sharing

⁹ <https://www.amazon.co.uk/clouddrive/home/>

¹⁰ <https://www.rackspace.com/cloud/block-storage>

¹¹ <http://opendefinition.org/guide/>

The principal motivation for the implementation of an IDR as a service at UCT is to enable sharing and reuse of research data (especially NRF-funded research data) in an open access repository. By definition, all data in the repository should therefore be made available without restriction (under a ¹²[Creative Commons license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/)), with exceptions being considered upon request. Routinely, it can be envisaged that embargo periods will be necessary to enable a period of privileged use, in line with current ¹³[Scholarly Communications guidelines and practices](http://www.openaccess.lib.uct.ac.za/oa/guides-faqs). The ability to restrict access to already ingested data, and more importantly the ability to automatically lift embargoes after a set period, especially if no data manager or curation workflow exists, are thus desired features of the repository software solution.

Apart from publishing finalised datasets, repositories can also serve as workspaces where data are stored and accessed throughout an active project. Encouraging such practises goes a long way to ensuring that data are not only properly managed, but also that the research process itself is open to scrutiny if the preliminary work is published alongside the final data. Such applications are possible within some repository software solutions, but also through integration with external services, such as the ¹⁴[Open Science Framework](https://osf.io/) (see Potential Software Solutions below). Addressing the challenges of sharing, versioning and collaborating on raw data within large teams is one of the main goals of such software. Maintaining the privacy of these preliminary data is another challenge and is of paramount importance to maintaining trust between data managers and researchers.

Analysis/Access to Content

Repositories often enable functionality far beyond simply storing data files. This is particularly true of sites hosting special collections, which generally present content in a graphically rich and sometimes interactive format. Domain-specific repositories, if supported by an active community, or centrally-funded facility, also tend to allow a number of ways of interacting with data, and often provide tools for analysis and visualisation of data from within the user interface. Although desirable, due to the breadth of the envisaged user base of the UCT IDR, it is unlikely that such interactivity will be possible. A foreseeable exception comprises tabular data and coordinates, which can both be graphed and plotted by several of

¹² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

¹³ <http://www.openaccess.lib.uct.ac.za/oa/guides-faqs>

¹⁴ <https://osf.io/>

the more generic repository software packages. Where interest is shown, it would be highly beneficial to have sufficient flexibility in the framework to enable researchers to write their own plugins or modules for the UCT IDR, which means that a customisable software solution is preferred in this regard.

Software is as much a part of a research project as the data themselves, and constitutes a necessary preservation artefact if the entire scientific workflow is to be shared and reused by others in future. Built-in version control, or at least a way to link to specific versions of software in public software repositories, is therefore also desirable.

Submission/Ingestion

Depending on the nature of the dataset to be ingested, the ingest process will vary in complexity. In the majority of cases it is likely that a web interface will be used to upload data, but for batch uploads of large numbers of files (by the data managers), a client program or API (¹⁵[application programming interface](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_programming_interface)) will be required. Sharing of repository contents with other repositories wishing to link to the UCT IDR, such as the NRF or other content aggregators, will also require the presence of an API.

The maximum file size to be hosted in the UCT IDR is also an important consideration, if storage allocations are to be made freely available to researchers, as capacity will be limited to the initial capital investment. On the other hand, if storage costs are recovered then the underlying hardware can scale with the size of the repository.

As discussed above, quality metadata are critical to ensuring the findability and ultimately the usefulness of data housed in a repository. In addition to policy acknowledgements that should be presented to authors during an upload, it is essential that data cannot be uploaded without minimum prescribed metadata. Therefore, repository software solutions that have the ability to enforce and set compulsory metadata submission upon data ingest are preferred. Ideally, these standards would be decided upon by the research communities and adopted of their own accord, by enabling the feature in their respective curation workflows.

¹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_programming_interface

PRECEDENTS

It is informative to consider what platforms other universities and research institutions around the world have chosen to house and share their research data. Since Re3Data is regarded as a definitive global registry of research data repositories worldwide, this list was chosen as a starting point for exploring which software solutions are popular choices for offering research data repositories as institutional services. The results in *Table 1* (appended) were created by filtering the Re3Data registry to display only university-wide institutional data repositories.

Of the 156 institutional data repositories registered with Re3Data.org, ¹⁶[DSpace](http://www.dspace.org/) is the most popular software choice, with 28 recorded instances. ¹⁷[Dataverse](http://dataverse.org/) is also popular (20 registered repositories), while ¹⁸[Fedora](http://fedorarepository.org/) is less popular (11 registrations). Along with ¹⁹[EPrints](http://www.eprints.org/uk/index.php/eprints-software/), these software solutions make up the top four repository software choices (by number) for institutional data repositories registered with Re3Data. Since a number of the institutional repository software registrations are listed as *other*, and considering that ²⁰[Figshare](https://figshare.com/) is not a filter option, universities known to be using Figshare for Institutions have also been included in the table.

Although Table 1 is selective and does not include all institutional repositories worldwide, it still provides insight into trends for choosing research data repository software. The following can be deduced from the data:

- American universities favour Dataverse for research data, while for research publications, most of them favour Dspace.
- European universities favour DSpace and most of them offer the same repository for submitting and sharing research data and publications.
- EPrints is chosen mostly in cases where the university's research publication repository was already built on EPrints.

¹⁶ <http://www.dspace.org/>

¹⁷ <http://dataverse.org/>

¹⁸ <http://fedorarepository.org/>

¹⁹ <http://www.eprints.org/uk/index.php/eprints-software/>

²⁰ <https://figshare.com/>

- Fedora is used as a specialist repository solution for hosting both research data and publications from the same repository, and has been implemented most commonly where funding, support staff and resources are prevalent.
- DSpace is still the most popular software choice for institutional *research publication* repositories, even in cases where the institutional *research data* repository is built on another software.

This data avails that institutions in particular regions have preferred data repository platforms, but that there is no unanimous solution. However, it is clear that Dspace, Fedora, Dataverse and Figshare are the most popular research data repository solutions, having found widespread support among leading universities worldwide.

POTENTIAL SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS

An exhaustive list of all possible repository software solutions is beyond the scope of this report. Our list of proposed candidates is based primarily on what we ascertained to be the most common choices for institutional repository platforms at universities around the world. We have included a mix of both open-source repository software solutions, as well as SaaS repository software solutions, which are becoming more popular as cloud offerings mature. It is also important to consider that due to active development communities and headway being made by the worldwide open science movement, repository software changes rapidly, adapting to the requirements of the international research and publishing communities. Therefore, the following descriptions can only be considered current and relevant for the immediate future.

Dspace (developed by ²¹[Duraspace](http://duraspace.org)) is a popular digital repository software for long-term storage, dissemination, and preservation of institutional research outputs. Dspace is built from Java web applications and programs, which maintain asset and metadata stores, and is interfaced by either Java-based or XML-based web front-ends. While it is known for being a turnkey solution, as a dedicated repository system it is lauded for its support of features, such as interoperability standards. Although hosted solutions have recently been offered by Duraspace, the majority of Dspace repositories are hosted locally by institutions, and connect to their local storage resources.

Fedora (also developed by Duraspace) can be regarded as a more flexible, extensible and scalable version of Dspace and has been developed with user interface extensibility in mind. It is a repository back-end with a choice of open-source front-ends that have been developed to suit specific repository requirements for servicing a wide range of disciplines, data-types and/or communities. Fedora has a large support community, the majority of which is concentrated within research institutions and a number of ‘solution packages’ exist as plug-ins that enable features such as visualisation and data analysis, as well as integrations for preservation software solutions, such as Archivematica. Since Fedora offers such extensive customisation capacity and entails the development of integrations from a vast range of

²¹ <http://duraspace.org/technologies/whats-the-repository-for-me>

options, the implementation, maintenance and upgrade of a Fedora-based repository entails dedicated institutional commitment to IT staffing and resources over the long-term.

Dataverse is an open-source web application for sharing, preserving, discovering and analysing research data, developed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science at Harvard University. Datasets are housed within so-called ‘dataverses’ along with descriptive metadata. The hierarchical organisation of the dataverses, which can contain further dataverses, has made it popular with institutions wanting to offer their researchers dedicated departmental or research group spaces for publishing and showcasing their outputs.

²²[DRYAD](http://datadryad.org) is an extensively customised version of Dspace, which undertakes to provide access to data at no cost, but charges for data submission to offset the costs of providing long-term data preservation. DRYAD for Organizations was developed to publish the research data underlying research articles that have been published commercially. Implementation of DRYAD for Organizations as an institutional data repository requires that the university has a commercial academic press and that only data linked to commercial research publications may be shared through the institutional DRYAD repository. As a consequence, DRYAD finds common usage as a data repository linked to commercial research publications.

Figshare hosts an open-access and free data repository for self-publishing and sharing of research outputs. Institutions desiring their own locally branded and managed repositories, however, have to pay for hosting and support services. Figshare for Institutions entails a large annual license fee, and UCT have reportedly been quoted the equivalent of at least R800 000 per annum, excluding the storage costs associated with archiving and preserving submitted data. Integrations already exist for a number of data collaboration, management and preservation tools, and any further integration requests are seriously considered by Figshare staff.

²³[Zenodo](https://zenodo.org) is a general-purpose, free hosted SaaS repository, offering free storage (within limits) aimed at supporting the self-publication of individual or group research projects. It

²² <http://datadryad.org/pages/membershipOverview>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/features>

was originally built on top of ²⁴[Invenio](http://invenio-software.org/) as a means of organising and distributing the outputs from ²⁵[CERN](https://home.cern/about). Although institutions wishing to publish their data collections under their own names can do so in Zenodo, using the so-called ‘Communities’ feature, universities requiring a dedicated institutional repository, or wanting to issue DOIs with institutional prefixes, will have to install and maintain a local instance of the open-source software (Invenio), with their own storage solution.

²⁶[TIND Institutional Repository](https://tind.io/repository) is a commercial SaaS (Software as a Service) repository solution, developed as a spin-off to Zenodo, as a result of institutional demand for extensive in-house customisation of the open-source software, Invenio. The annual license fee (\$35 000) includes up to 15 TB of cloud-based data hosting with back-up and once-off customisation of deposit forms, DOIs, collections, communities and implementation of the institutional user interface. Also included are on-going maintenance, upgrades and 24/7 support.

²⁷[Oneshare](https://www.dataone.org/sites/default/files/member-nodes/documents/Member_Node_Description_Form_ONEShare_v1.1_20150408.pdf) is the research data repository of the ²⁸[California Digital Library](http://www.cdlib.org/about/). Like Zenodo, it is an open repository built on open-source software, but it cannot be adopted as another university’s institutional repository. It is therefore a repository service which individual researchers may use to self-publish their data.

²⁹[Globus](https://www.globus.org/providers) is primarily a solution for moving large volumes of data between research sites. Although the means for doing this have existed prior to Globus, the ease of use and management insights provided by the interface have made it a popular choice for sharing data via grid-FTP. The ability to move large volumes of data quickly has led to Globus expanding into the data publication space. They now offer the ability to establish collections with associated curation, access, and metadata policies, issuing of DOIs and linking to ORCIDs. Collections are built by adding datasets (transferred from different locations or instruments

²⁴ <http://invenio-software.org/>

²⁵ <https://home.cern/about>

²⁶ <https://tind.io/repository>

²⁷ https://www.dataone.org/sites/default/files/member-nodes/documents/Member_Node_Description_Form_ONEShare_v1.1_20150408.pdf

²⁸ <http://www.cdlib.org/about/>

²⁹ <https://www.globus.org/providers>

using Globus), which are indexed and available for search and recovery by others using the Globus service. This service is now offered as a commercial SaaS repository solution, so that no software has to be installed or operated locally. Existing storage resources can be utilised as endpoints and institutional identity management can be integrated. Current pricing for the cheapest implementation with Globus Data Publication is R144 000 per annum for 40 users and 40 TB per month. Their pricing model is however changing as they aim to move to a value/feature-based charge, compared to the current data volume-based calculation.

³⁰[CKAN](http://ckan.org/) is an open-source repository software that is built with Python on the backend and Javascript on the frontend. PostgreSQL is its database engine and search is powered by SOLR. It has predominantly been implemented by national governments as a solution for making their data catalogues open to the public. The CKAN organisation ³¹[openly declares](http://ckan.org/files/2012/08/OKF-OR12-poster.pdf) that the software is not an institutional repository, although it still offers some of the features that institutions desire.

³²[OSF for Institutions](https://osf.io/4znzp/wiki/OSF%20for%20Institutions/) is not a data repository and does not aim to provide an excellent repository service, but offers a free online service concerned with ‘filling the gaps’ between research data management tools and services to enable really reproducible science. OSF integrates with a number of repository software solutions and is constantly developing further integrations with RDM tools and services. The OSF should therefore be implemented in conjunction with the UCT IDR and can assist with providing the features and considerations that the UCT IDR software solution does not, as well as enabling research data collaboration tools during the research project lifecycle.

³⁰ <http://ckan.org/>

³¹ <http://ckan.org/files/2012/08/OKF-OR12-poster.pdf>

³² <https://osf.io/4znzp/wiki/OSF%20for%20Institutions/>

EVALUATION

Although the considerations that go into choosing a repository software are manifold, several can be highlighted as critical to the decision making process and quickly eliminate potential solutions. Principally amongst these is the resourcing of the UCT IDR platform, not only from a capital and installation perspective, but also from an on-going support point of view. Hosted, Software as a Service (SaaS) models are clearly the easiest route to implementing a repository, with infrastructure services and even community support provided by the hosting company. The primary benefits include much shorter time to launch and greatly reduced start-up costs, as well as training opportunities for repository staff. Unfortunately, this convenience comes at a cost, with hosted repository services charging from at least R300 000 to R850 000 p.a. in our estimates. Discussions around Figshare for Institutions (estimated to cost at least R800 000 p.a.) showed that sustainable funding would likely not be available, given the current political and economic trends. Alternative solutions such as TIND (R500 000 p.a. all incl.), Globus (R286 000) and DRYAD (R600 000) are similarly unaffordable and cannot be implemented until a sustainable funding stream is identified. Commercial SaaS repository solutions therefore seem out of reach for the moment. Having said that, cost recovery is a model being pursued by a number of service offerings at UCT and is possibly a route to funding the UCT IDR license fees. The viability and sustainability of this model will require careful structuring and forecasting in order to ensure that it can be marketed to the research community.

On the other hand, it is important to realise that free hosted SaaS repository solutions do exist alongside the commercial offerings. Contrary to what might be expected, in most cases (e.g. Zenodo & Oneshare), the provider plans are not limited by the amount of storage available, but rather by the features they offer. Although sustainability should be a concern, the strong developer support, community uptake, as well as government funding for open science paradigms in Europe and America (where most free repositories emanate from), show no signs of abating. Repositories like Zenodo and Oneshare principally aim to further open science ideals by offering a home for datasets that might not otherwise be published. As such, they are shared global resources, which publicise all of their data equally and without bias. Institutions wishing to house their research outputs in such repositories are therefore limited to creating a community or subset among the repository's other, disparate communities.

Although some degree of branding is possible in these scenarios, for the most part, institutions wishing to present a strong institutional identity as an institutional data repository, are best served by locally installed repository solutions, such as commercial SaaS (discussed above) or open-source software solutions (discussed below). Furthermore, because DOIs are issued by free hosted SaaS repository platforms, institutions wanting to mint their own DOIs are also best served by a locally installed repository solution. For these reasons, and despite their low costs, free hosted SaaS solutions do not suit the mission of the UCT IDR. Nonetheless, we can create institutional communities and advertise free, hosted repository platforms to the research community as indispensable services for those who cannot afford to store their data with the UCT IDR or elsewhere.

In addition to the issues of branding and institutional identity, control over the curation workflows and copyright policies can only be efficiently achieved with a locally installed, open-source repository software solution. Depending on whether curation staff or data managers are available or not, it will be critical to provide tools for research communities to manage the publication process themselves if metadata standards and data quality are to be enforced. Equivalently, promoting open science ideals of sharing data will only be possible if data can be shared under default licenses and justification-prompts are required for any necessary exceptions. Deciding what metrics are tracked and integrating these into the institutional research management system, Converis, will also be easier to achieve with a locally installed repository solution.

Based on these considerations, and in spite of the attractiveness of hosted solutions for quickly setting up a functional repository, a locally installed, open-source software solution seems likely to be the most cost effective means towards fulfilling the UCT IDR mission statement. The remainder of this evaluation therefore covers a detailed investigation of the suitability of the proposed open-source software, and a detailed analysis of their features is presented in Table 2 (appended).

CKAN was developed specifically as a ‘data hub’ for making local, national and supranational government data open to the public. Although this software solution offers some desirable features, many of the essential features that we have considered will need to be developed and customised, causing concern over local capacity to implement the repository in line with

essential requirements. CKAN provides its own version of a basic metadata schema and harvesting functionalities, but requires further customisation for implementation of specific metadata schema and harvesting. Although code has been developed and shared openly for customisation capabilities (such as OAI-PMH), the ease of implementation for such enhancements is not known. Although built-in tools for visualisation, geo-spatial analysis and social media dissemination are desirable, such features have been developed to specifically suit the display of government data types. Since CKAN is not primarily intended to be used as an institutional repository, essential functionalities for managing and sharing research data, such as enabling periods of privileged use, and integration with Altmetrics, ORCID and Archivematica, are not offered. Furthermore, we have not found many installations of CKAN as an institutional repository and most implementations at universities serve ³³[discipline-specific repositories within academic institutions](#). A mere five instances of institutional CKAN repositories have been ³⁴[registered on Re3Data](#) and only two of those are offered as an institutional data repository (the remaining three are discipline-specific). As a result, the community using and developing the CKAN software is small and mostly contained within government organisations. Since the remaining open-source solutions offer more essential features, as well as easier ability to customise (with greater community support, especially within academic institutions), CKAN is not best suited to the mission of the UCT IDR.

Dspace is the most popular software choice for institutional repositories worldwide and has the largest support community of the repository options that we've compared. It is a safe choice in terms of national interoperability, since most local data repositories that have already been implemented (or are in the process of being implemented), are built on Dspace (e.g. CSIR, UP, UNISA) and have already been successfully tested against the NRF's harvesting system for issuing DOIs and facilitating a national research data registry. An 'out-of-the-box' Dspace installation enables a branded institutional repository that covers the basic requirements for data submission, metadata creation, archiving, and sharing. Support for communities and collections is built into the software, integration tools for Archivematica have been developed by the community, advanced search features and engine optimisation are supported, and dissemination and linking of data are made possible through API, OAI-PMH, and RSS functionalities. A major strength of the Dspace software is its reporting

³³ <http://ckan.org/instances/#>

³⁴ <http://service.re3data.org/search?query=&software%5B%5D=CKAN&types%5B%5D=institutional>

functionality, with the ability to set customised automatic repository reports, as well as to integrate Altmetrics badges and link with ORCID profiles. Dspace, as a turnkey software solution is, however, limited to data download only. It does not easily support data visualisation or analysis from within the repository interface (although some functionality is achievable through development), and structuring of compound objects is not well supported. The ability to reuse data therefore depends on the software available to the user, as well as their understanding of the data as it is described by the metadata. An efficient Dspace repository therefore relies on the provision of complex metadata functionality, where mandatory metadata fields need to be customised to enable understandability and reusability of the data, but the extent to which metadata functionality can be customised in Dspace cannot be evaluated until tested. Of the repository software solutions that we have covered, Dspace has the least extensive set of add-on features and will require customisation to suit different user needs as they arise in the future, causing concern over its eventual sustainability (especially with regard to maintaining customised features throughout upgrades). It is, however, a recommended software solution to implement if resources are limited and if an easily installable solution is desired.

Fedora has been developed with user interface extensibility in mind, and therefore suits the needs of a repository that serves a wide range of disciplines, data-types and communities. Fedora essentially covers all of the features that Dspace provides, but with an option to fill the gaps in Dspace through development of a range of additional features, customisations, solution packages and plugins. Whereas DSpace provides datasets for download (and further processing relies on the user's own resources), Fedora provides options to develop data visualisation within the repository, enabling many types of file formats to be read and analysed from within the browser, as well as offering capability for structuring and ordering compound objects within the repository interface. Although not as vast as the Dspace community, Fedora has a large support community, the majority of which is concentrated within research institutions who are working together towards developing solutions to mutual repository concerns. An institutional repository built on Fedora can offer a range of discipline-specific customisations, integrations and features, as well as further integration of separate institutional repositories and potential for aggregating a university-wide data registry. Depending on the user interface chosen, Fedora communities are constantly developing solutions for integrating the software with data creation, collaboration, management and

archiving tools. ³⁵[Archidora](#) enables the integration of the Fedora-³⁶[Islandora](#) package with preservation software, Archivematica. Integration tools are also currently being developed for the Fedora-³⁷[Hydra](#) package. Using Fedora as an institutional repository software therefore provides opportunity for streamlining and automating workflows all the way from data submission, through to ingestion, display and preservation of data, with the added benefit of creating customised repository collections per community that can be aggregated and searched from within one repository landing page. The future offers custom Fedora-based repository solutions from communities that have come together to develop out-of-the-box repository solutions for robust, trusted Fedora-based research data repository solutions, such as ³⁸[Hydra-in-a-box](#) (currently under development). Although a packaged solution (i.e. one that is developed by research support staff with mutual requirements and concerns) is attractive, such solutions cannot be considered and implemented until development is completed. In the meantime, Fedora presents a repository solution with offerings that cover the largest range of considerations, but with the most demand on institutional staff and resources, due to the complexity of the software, choice of user-interfaces and the extensive add-on options.

Dataverse is a favourable option for the integration of tier 2 (regional) data repositories (see British Columbia's ³⁹[Abacus Dataverse](#)), due to the ability to easily brand repository nodes (so-called 'Dataverses') within one regional Dataverse. Data curation workflows are streamlined from data creation, collaboration and management, through to analysis and publication, with the ability to easily create communities/collections and assign curation roles within each. Dataverse offers some customisation ability, especially with respect to user-interface design, featured communities and skinning of group Dataverses. Although it is seemingly not as extensively customisable as Fedora, it offers attractive customisation options with less demand for local IT support. The extent to which data can be visualised from within the repository browser is unknown, but features such as geo-tagging, geo-analysis and visualisation of tabular data are built-in. Further customisation requires active developer input, but on-going maintenance of the out-of-the-box software solution appears to be

³⁵ <https://github.com/Islandora-Labs/archidora>

³⁶ <http://islandora.ca/CLAW>

³⁷ <https://projecthydra.org/>

³⁸ <http://hydrainabox.projecthydra.org/>

³⁹ <https://dvn.library.ubc.ca/dvn/>

relatively simple. Dataverse is also highly attractive due to its current and ⁴⁰[planned integration](#) capabilities. It integrates with both OSF and DataCite, while integration tools are in development for DMPtool, DMPonline, Globus, Altmetric, Archivematica and ⁴¹[iRODS](#). Although ORCID integration is not currently supported, future development has been planned. Established integration with OSF is a major advantage, especially with respect to preservation and archiving considerations, since datasets published in the UCT IDR can be linked directly to the full record of the research project's data stored in OSF, enabling full transparency of the data (all previous and working versions), and assisting with the reproducibility and validity of the final dataset that will be hosted in the UCT IDR. Integration of the UCT IDR with OSF will ultimately assist issues associated with storage and preservation to the extent that the UCT IDR will only house data that is directly linked to a research publication, but provides a link to the full collection of research data that is stored and backed-up by OSF. Furthermore, ⁴²[Planned integration](#) for Dataverse with Archivematica will enable data to be transformed to open formats and preserved well into the future. Dataverse also offers publication workflows that can be customised per research community and controlled to varying degrees through the assignment of community curators, with less demand on repository staff than required by Fedora. Data can be openly or privately disseminated with assignment of local DOIs and can be linked with relevant repositories/registries via API and OAI-PMH functionality, however, this potential interoperability still needs to be tested against the NRF's current infrastructure. Dataverse offers some reporting functionality (tracking and usage downloads), but further reporting capabilities, such as customisation of automatic stakeholder reports will remain unknown until tested.

It is obvious from our cursory investigation of these four repository solutions that, although at a basic level they offer similar capabilities for data management and publication, they each have unique features and extended capabilities, as well as varying levels of demand from an operational point of view. Having said that, it is clear that each solution has something unique to offer and is a viable candidate for building an institutional data repository at UCT.

⁴⁰ <http://scholar.harvard.edu/mercecosas/presentations/connecting-dataverse-research-life-cycle>

⁴¹ <http://irods.org/>

⁴² <https://wiki.archivematica.org/Dataverse>

Regardless of which software is selected for a locally installed UCT IDR, it is important to recognise the costs associated with this option. Unlike commercial SaaS solutions, which charge on-going fees, local installation of an open-source solution will require significant, initial upfront investment in hardware, and a commitment to replacing hardware in future. A hybrid model could also be envisaged, whereby storage is sought from a cloud vendor. While this would incur on-going fees, it would require less maintenance and oversight from IT staff, since the infrastructure is offered as a complete service. The costs and availability of advanced IT and programming skills also have to be considered, as at least some customisation of the repository software solution is foreseeable.

RECOMMENDATION

From our investigations, it is obvious that the features and relevant merits of the different repository software solutions are impossible to weigh up on the basis of published feature sets, and depend heavily on the implementation resources and user communities' needs. It is therefore important that we clarify the resources available to implement and operate the UCT IDR before it is commissioned.

In particular, the decision between commercial SaaS or a locally installed open-source repository software is difficult to assess and has important implications for the sustainability of the repository. Although it is tempting to dismiss commercial SaaS solutions as too expensive, the costs of replicating similar services locally must be carefully considered. In particular, their undertaking to store and archive data, as well as to act as accredited repositories comes at significant expense, which cannot easily be replicated locally without incurring significant infrastructure and staffing costs. Hybrid models, with storage provided by a cloud company, will also attract on-going fees and, most importantly, require upfront purchases to ensure longevity of data access.

Free hosted SaaS repository platforms offer a third approach to setting up a data repository, with the benefits of cost reduction and rapid implementation. However, this comes at the cost of not being perceived as an institutional repository, and furthermore upon condition of surrendering control over the long-term preservation of institutional data. Considerations such as these lead us to believe that although the mission of the UCT IDR is clear, without a carefully planned business model and risk assessment, the choice of a repository software solution for the UCT IDR is unlikely to be obvious.

Recommendation 1: Drafting of a business model for the repository with a clear outline for funding and sustainability.

Following on from implementation of this recommendation, the evaluations in this report inform the possible solutions, which fall into the following scenarios:

(1) National funding or institutional support is available for operating the repository

a. Commercial SaaS e.g. Figshare/TIND

- Subscription to annual SaaS plan
- Storage included in provider plan
- No local IT staff required and systems are maintained and upgraded by hosting company
- Training and support offered by hosting company
- Customisations carried out at cost by hosting company
- Dedicated institutional curation staff to oversee submissions and metadata standards

b. Locally hosted repository service

- Employment of dedicated IT and repository management staff
- Local storage and compute infrastructure including provision for backups, or hybrid model where these are provided by cloud providers at cost
- Local support and training
- Access to, or funding for, software development capacity for repository customisation
- Provision for skills development capacity building and engagement with international development efforts, e.g. open-source community sprints
- Integration development for local archiving and preservation systems
- Dedicated institutional curation staff to oversee submissions and metadata standards

(2) No funding or support is available and costs will be recovered from repository users

a. Locally hosted open-source repository solution

- Cost model with pay-for-deposit
- Local or cloud storage
- Potential for support and administration staff depending on business model
- Customisations at cost to users
- Integration with local archiving and preservation systems

- Institutional IT staff manage the upgrades and maintenance of customised features
- No verification of submitted data, but repository staff encourage assignment of community curators

(3) No funding is available and no costs can/will be recovered.

- a. Free hosted SaaS
 - Create institutional communities within free online SaaS platforms
 - Libraries/eResearch staff assist with access and advice
 - No (or little) institutional branding
 - DOIs are minted with SaaS prefixes
 - No customisation

Before funding is secured or a business model is evaluated and approved, it is our recommendation that we proceed in the interim with the implementation and parallel evaluation of the locally installed open-source solutions that were identified in the evaluation section (Dspace, Fedora, Dataverse).

Recommendation 2: Comparative installation of bare-bones open-source repositories: Dspace, Fedora, and Dataverse

Although this report has endeavoured to be as thorough as possible, interrogation of functionalities has been limited to the descriptions provided by the authors. For instance, software support for functionalities such as auto-lift of embargoes, policy and agreement pop-ups, and the extent to which metadata and licensing can be customised will remain undetermined until we can test these features during implementation. It is envisaged that detailed assessment of their relative suitability and associated resourcing requirements will only be possible in our own hands and we therefore recommend installation of Dspace, Fedora and Dataverse to be tested in comparison. Furthermore, since free hosted SaaS solutions generally offer little customisation and control of data workflows, their usefulness could also be quickly evaluated in parallel with these local open-source installations.

Recommendation 3: Form UCT community/collections within free SaaS repositories to evaluate their suitability and provide free alternatives.

Considering that the parallel implementation and testing of open-source repository solutions will take significant time, it is suggested that a free hosted SaaS trial begins as soon as possible, by forming UCT community collections within a small selection of specific free SaaS repository platforms, such as Zenodo. These would serve to support the immediate publication and sharing of research data from within the institution while the UCT IDR evaluation continues, and could continue as an option for researchers to share their data, alongside the main local institutional offering when it is deployed. This would offer an important, free alternative for those researchers unable to afford publication in the UCT IDR in the eventuality that a charge model will be pursued. Publication and preservation of software has also been highlighted as important in this report and free version control software repositories can help meet this goal. The creation of a UCT community within free platforms like ⁴³[Bitbucket](https://bitbucket.org/) could therefore similarly assist with enabling access to, and reusability of, data-as-a-service to UCT research groups. The extent to which software, data, and written publications can be linked together from their locations within and outside the UCT IDR will also need to be thoroughly investigated.

Recommendation 4: Engage with select research communities to seek their input on the suitability of the UCT IDR solutions for sharing their research data.

As part of the evaluations we believe it would be constructive to seek input from the researchers who will be making use of the UCT IDR. Their feedback, as individuals and as communities, will be invaluable in choosing an appropriate solution. The views of the university administration are important too, and will also need to be considered if specific reporting, citation tracking, and other administration features are required. However, without consulting the end-users we run the risk of building an institutional data repository that suits the research managers and support staff, but not the researchers themselves. To this end, calls for collaboration should be extended to select relevant research communities or groups with

⁴³ <https://bitbucket.org/>

whom we will develop ⁴⁴[data curation profiles](#) to assess their needs and against which we will test the repositories' capabilities. Assessing the potential for customising the UCT IDR to meet the needs of UCT's diverse research communities is a critical goal during this phase of the evaluation.

Recommendation 5: OSF should be launched alongside the UCT IDR.

The OSF, although not an appropriate software for the UCT IDR, enables research collaboration and streamlines workflows between research project stakeholders. Since it already integrates with a number of other SaaS and cloud storage services (such as ⁴⁵[Google Drive](#), ⁴⁶[Dropbox](#), Dataverse & Figshare), the OSF is undoubtedly a useful tool to include as part of the UCT IDR service. Most importantly, because the OSF provides free storage and preservation services for institutions, it is a potential solution to issues of storage costs associated with implementing an institutional data repository. For instance, the OSF could house and preserve raw data while the UCT IDR only retains the finalised, smaller datasets, thereby reducing institutional data storage requirements, while at the same time encouraging sharing of supporting data. We therefore recommend including the implementation and use of OSF during the UCT IDR test phases.

In summary, we suggest that the following actions are required to implement an IDR for the UCT community:

- (1) Resource evaluation and modelling of a sustainable business plan for the UCT IDR**
- (2) Installation of Dspace, Fedora and Dataverse locally at UCT to test in parallel**
- (3) Creation of UCT communities within online, free hosted SaaS repositories**
- (4) Engagement with research communities to test the repository solutions**
- (5) Uptake of OSF services with associated outreach and training**

⁴⁴ <http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/dcptoolkit/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.google.com/drive/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.dropbox.com/>